

Migration and its Complications with special reference to youth of Punjab

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Despite the significant benefits of migration, some migrants remain among the most vulnerable members of society. Migrants are often the first to lose their jobs in the event of an economic downturn. Some work for less pay, for longer hours, and in worse conditions than native-born workers. While migration is often an empowering experience, some migrants endure human rights violations, abuse, and discrimination. Migrants, particularly women and children, may fall victim to human trafficking and the heinous forms of exploitation that it entails.

Types of Migration:

1. Internal Migration: Moving within a Nation.
2. External Migration: Moving to a different Nations.
3. Seasonal Migration: Moving with each season or In response to labourer demand or climate change.

In today's time, almost every home in Punjab somehow has their relation with abroad. The first Sikh settlers from Punjab are mostly those people who were hired by British authorities around 1830 to get the work done in farmlands of Australia but There are no authentic sources from where it can be confirmed that early Punjabi's workers were worked in Australia's farmlands.

Key Words: youth, migration

Introduction

Migration is not a term, it's a process. As far as the early 17th-century Latin term *migrare* is considered, it simply means to move or shift. There can be ample reasons why one decides to migrate but the foremost reason according to me are desire. The desire to live a better life; the desire to earn a better living. And to desire is beautiful because it requires one to step out of their comfort zone. In today's increasingly interconnected world, international migration has become a reality that touches nearly all corners of the globe. Modern transportation has made it easier, cheaper and faster for people to move in search of jobs, opportunity, education, and quality of life. At the same time conflict, poverty, inequality and a lack of sustainable livelihoods compel people to leave their homes to seek a better future for themselves and their families abroad. When supported by appropriate policies, migration can contribute to inclusive and sustainable economic growth and development in both home and host communities². The migration process not only brings people close to each other but it also exchanges the ideas and culture of one nation generation with other nation generation which give birth to something stunning. For instance, The Afro-American generation gave birth to break dance and freestyle clothes which gave a new wave to American dance and fashion industries. There are many examples around the world which proved that when two different culture are assimilated with each other it's always gonna

be a masterpiece.

Migration policy is at the top of the global political agenda. More than 1 million people tried to cross the Mediterranean to reach Europe from 2014-2016. This has been largely caused by the displacement of people from war-torn countries such as Syria, Afghanistan, Yemen, Bangladesh, etc. Population migration is an important issue for local planners and nationally. Locally changes in the size and composition of populations relative movement between areas impact on the need for services including housing, social health, education, employment, etc. knowledge of population movement is also critical to properly assess the success of regeneration initiative although, historically, adequate data have not been available.

Migration from Punjab:

In today's time, almost every home in Punjab somehow has their relation with abroad. The first Sikh settlers from Punjab are mostly those people who were hired by British authorities around 1830 to get the work done in farmlands of Australia but There are no authentic sources from where it can be confirmed that early Punjabi's (The word Punjabi's refer to those people who can speak punjabi or living in Punjab) workers were worked in Australia's farmlands⁶. Shortly, after the annexation of Punjab into the British Raj in 1849. The Britishers started recruiting the local Punjabi's into their armies to serve the British Kingdom. The migration of Punjabi's was escalated during World War I & World

War II. When Britain was in war with Germany and they need an army to stand against Germany so they started recruiting the local people from Punjab and India in enormous numbers. In World War I and World War II Punjabi's fought at many 9 frontier against the Axis power. The composition of British Indian Army was mostly filled by Punjabis. For instance, In opium wars Punjabi's fought against the China Emperor, during this war Punjabi's were popular as "BLACK LIONS". After the end of World War II most of the Punjabi's who settle down in Britain and other European countries were from military background. People wanted to leave the Punjab not just because there was a shortage of industrial and agricultural jobs, but also because of the chaotic aftermath of the 1947 division of "British" India into the secular but largely Hindu state of India and the Muslim state of Pakistan. The frontier between India and Pakistan ran through the Sikh homeland of the Punjab. There was bloodshed and destruction as millions of Muslims, Hindus and Sikhs tried to cross the border to the safety of their own communities. The Punjab changed from a settled and prosperous area to a violent and overcrowded frontier zone.

Many Sikhs left the area that was to become Pakistan to move to the Indian section of the Punjab, while others left India altogether. As time passes, developed countries opened many new ways for others or outsiders and Punjabi's take full advantage of this opportunities. In now a days the popular way to go to abroad is by student visa. In which people initially go for study and later then they apply for the citizenship for that country to get the permanent residence.

Hypothesis

The migration from Punjab was started in late 1830 but in previous 10 years to today's Punjab people are crazy about to go abroad especially Canada. By following this trend in Punjab we made the following hypothesis to know the ground situation.

1. Youth are going abroad to improve their financial situation in home country.
2. After getting in touch with western, Punjab's culture is assimilated with western culture

Objectives of the Study

The main objectives of the study are to review the present patterns of youth migration from Punjab. This objective is to investigate overall effect of western culture on Punjab's traditions along this there is also a secondary motive that is how fast this acculturation happening in Punjab. Through snowball

sampling we have collected samples from various region from Punjab was selected for the study. The study mainly aims to investigate their causes, migration pattern and to know the culture changes.

1. Why the youth of Punjab going away from Punjab
2. To study the culture changes among the migrant population in terms of lifestyle, language and traditions.

The survey on youth migration from Punjab is completed by 200 respondents from various countries such as Canada, Australia, etc. The sample was obtained by snowball sampling. Any kind of incentives were not offered to the respondents to take part in a hard to convince respondents to take part in this survey. After analyzing responses carefully, we used the relevant information for the research.

Causes of Migration

Majid Husain states are also going to abroad to settle their life. According to Majid Hussain, the main causes of migration is advanced technology, poor economic conditions in the hs that in today's world the human migration has big concern to every country. Many countries are going through a civil war which pushes the people towards the developed countries to improve their financial conditions and to live an ideal lifestyle. Majid Hussain points out that people also go abroad to improve their lifestyle, for the future of their children and high skilled people from various fieldome country, political instability and less per capita resources, etc.

Immigration, Migration, and Culture

The writer of this article emphasis on cultural assimilation into other societies and communities. The term Immigration refers specifically to international migration that is relatively permanent in nature. Immigrants are those individuals who have moved to a new country on a relatively permanent base. Migration often results in two or more cultures coming into contact in the process of acculturation one party have to lose their culture to adjust in the new culture.

Psychological theory and research suggest that acculturation is bi-dimensional, with changes potentially taking place along two dimensions - One representing the maintenance or loss of the original culture and other representing the adoption or rejection of the new culture but some people not adopt the new culture instead of adopting new culture they maintain their original culture. The two culture may be expressed at different times, in a different context or may merge to form cultural expression that has

aspects of both cultures.

Is Migration Beneficial Or Detrimental To The Host Country?

The writers has written that gives benefit to the host country because when migration happen people bring new culture and new innovative ideas to the host country. They write that human resource is the supreme resources among all other natural resources because human knows that how to use the other natural resources which helps the host country to enhance their progress. Writers suggests that immigration fueled diversity which is good for economic growth. The migration of old people is not good for the host country because government has to spend money on old people's health, pension and on other welfare activities. However, the migration of youth is always give benefit to the hostcountry because youth are skilled and innovative which enhance the progress of host country.

Linguistic Proximity on Preferred Destination

An extensive literature shows that both fluency in destination language and the transfer to existing human capital to the destination countries 'labour market' (Bleaky and Chin 2004). They started that language effect the migrant in destination country because all migrant have to communicate in the mother tongue of that country. Alicia and Mariola Pytikova collect the data of 30 OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development) countries who shares the same official language such as USA and U.K and 40 million people migrated to OECD countries who did not share any common languages.

The Benefit of Migration

Migration and Integration have lasting effects on economic social process. In this the writers scrutinize if a diverse cultural environment has a positive impact on labour market provide new opportunities through an open and tolerant climate and contributing to overall economic growth. They test their

Family Occupation in Home Country

It is crystal clear that most of the respondents have their background from the agriculture sector but the main question arrive here that why there were so many respondents from the agriculture sector. The simple answer for this that farmers families are suffering in India and Punjab because they can't get the appropriate price for their crops which not enough to run their lives. they borrow money from money lenders to send their children to abroad To them, it is an only

assumption by analysing the successful transition from education to work depending on the regional distribution and ethnic mix of the foreign population in Germany (cultural diversity). To account for variation within Germany, cultural diversity is observed at small administrative units. We analyse a cohort of young adults at the time of the successful completion of their apprenticeship in Germany and follow them through the beginning of their career. The concentration on a homogenous group regarding occupational certificates enables us to focus on the effects of the local and social environment as well as individual characteristics such as their national background on finding a job (or not). They apply an instrumental variable design to disentangle the effects of cultural diversity and share of foreigners. The results show that both young foreigners and Germans face significantly lower barriers for employment entry in culturally more diverse German regions.

Migration and Social Change

As cultural evolutionist interested in how societies change over the long term. We have thought a lot about migration, but only recently tumbled to an obvious idea: migration has a profound effect on how societies evolve culturally because it is selective. Writers believe that immigration generates far more cultural evolution today than does conquest. Flows of migrants are often substantial. Foreign-born people, mainly from Latin America and Asia, compose about 11% of the current US population, a figure close to historical averages. The richer countries of Europe, such as Sweden, Norway and Germany, once the source of streams of immigrants to the United States and elsewhere, are now receiving people from Asia, Africa and poorer European countries such as Poland and the Balkan states.

one-time investment which is roughly around ₹15 - 18 lakh (Indian rupee). On the flip side of the coin, their parents are not willing to allow their children into the same occupation which they are doing from the years. second one portion is showing the Government jobs sector which is very less in numbers as compared to opposite occupation. The reason behind is this that they have their permanent source of income but farmers families doesn't have any permanent source of income.

Figure: family occupation in home country

Motivating Factors behind Migration

Figure 4 illustrate that main behind the migration of all respondents were the economical factors. There is a direct relationship between figure 3 & 4 which is this that most of the respondents families are from agriculture sector and the revenue from crops are not so good to spend a good life in

India or punjab. To improve their financial situation in home country they come to abroad to earn money and take the full advantage of good economy of developed countries.

The second most prefer choice is for a good lifestyle which is very low as compare to opposite choice which means that the main motive of all respondents are just to earn money.

Figure: Motivating Factor behind Migration

The Changes, Respondents are not willing to do

It can be clearly seen that most of the respondents are not willing to change their religion but they agree that they can marry to those who are not even to belong their religion or from their native country. For instance, In the starting of phase 1900s Punjabi migrated to United States Of America for work, when 1913 California state passed the California Alien Land Act 1913 after that Asians were not allowed to work, they were not considered as

citizens and it was also illegal for Punjabis laborers to bring wives from Punjab. At last most of punjabis labors of America ended up with marrying Mexican girls but they did not force them to change their religion for marriage, Punjabi Sikh-Mexican American community fading into history. In figure, 40% respondents are not willing to change their religion but on the other hand 60% respondents are not willing to change anything.

3.5 The Changes, Respondents are not willing to do

Figure: the changes, respondents are not willing to do

Changes In Mother Tongue

It is crystal clear 55% respondents admitted that they see changes in their in mother tongue and 22% respondents don't know that his mother tongue and English is mixing up with each other. 26% respondent are

still think that there is no changes in their mother tongue. Most long-term migrants know whatit's like to be a slightly rusty native speaker. The process seems obvious: the longer you are away, the more your language suffers.

3.6 Changes In Mother Tongue

Figure Changes In Mother tongue

Tradition Need A Change

Considering the statistical data our respondents agree, our tradition need change. The interesting fact of this question is this out 70 female respondents 40 female respondents agree, need a change in our tradition. Maybe the main cause behind this of females is this, they are not getting enough freedom in their home country to do their work. Additionally, our male respondents also want a change in tradition. Out of 120 male respondents, 50 male agrees that there must be the change in society and only one respondent agrees for no change.

Figure: Traditions need a change.

Most Important Changes Required For Adapting

Taking statistical data into account of figure 9, it is clear that when a person shifts from one place to another place he/she has to adjust according to the new environment. In data, respondents also agree that they also had

to adjust according to their new situations when they moved to a new country. As answers given by our respondents, they had to adjust their food habits, catching the flow of new language and most importantly that how people behave with each other.

Figure: most important changes required to adapting

Homecoming

Taking statistical data into account of figure 12 that most of the respondents are not in favour to return home after once they settled in abroad as i discussed earlier that most of people are going abroad to improve their

financial situation in home country. Out of 200 respondents, 110 respondents are favouring not to come home and only 10 respondent is willing to be back. Remaining 80 respondents are not sure about this.

3.11 Homecoming

Figure: Homecoming

Conclusion:

India has around 600 million youth which is more than any other country's youth population. Youth is the backbone of a country because they provide more people to the workforce than any other age groups and have better skills as compared to other age groups. It can be dangerous if they are not guided properly and the Indian government is failing to give them jobs which would make their living conditions better. Lack of jobs is creating unrest among youth and that is not good at any point. It eventually leads to the conflict between the government and youth of the nation.

The migration from Punjab began in late 1830 and it is still going on but this time the migration is at very fast pace than ever in Punjab history. The figures can be disputed but it's clear that Punjab is staring at a huge demographic crisis. It is being reported that around one lakh students have gone abroad especially to Canada to study and then to find employment. Most educational institutions here are complaining of a sharp drop in admissions. But the majority does not want to return. This unrest is going too far from where it can be impossible to recover the potential of our youth. The data of our report flavored my hypothesis that the prime reason behind youth migration from Punjab is economic factors and if we look into grass root level you will find out that Punjab government are not providing enough decent jobs to youth which will help to improve their financial situation. Most of the people who are going abroad belong from farmer's families because the Punjab Government is not paying enough for their crops and to sustain that they are sending their children abroad to earn money. The journey just not ended up here, after getting abroad they have to adjust in the culture of the host country. As people spend years in the host country, the culture of both communities is starting to assimilate with each other. Furthermore, Punjab's people also agree that they have seen changes in the mother tongue, dressing style, after getting in touch with western. Besides that, Punjab is gripping by drugs which mostly cover the young population of Punjab and to avoid this some parents forcefully send their children abroad. Some of our respondents think that in Punjab there is no scope for their children so they migrate from Punjab to secure their children future and without giving incentive to be respondent.

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